

ON THE PAPKOVICH–FADLE AND OTHER EIGENFUNCTIONS GENERATED BY THIRD FOURTH AND SIXTH ORDER DIFFERENTIAL SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Third, fourth and sixth order ordinary homogeneous differential systems defined over a finite y range, which generate eigenfunctions $\phi(y, \lambda_i)$ and eigenvalues λ_i . The properties of these eigenfunctions, denoted ϕ_i , are studied by considering boundary value problems. The governing partial differential equation prevailing throughout at the strips and the boundary conditions at the long edges are such that, a solution in the form of a product $\phi_i e^{\lambda_i x}$, ϕ_i is governed the ordinary system which is to be examined. Solutions to such boundary value problems are obtained for short edge condition(s) which are defined in terms of arbitrary data functions $F(y)$, $G(y)$ etc. In as much as the solutions for the strip problems exist, are unique and are expressible as a sum of such products, then by setting $x = 0$ they produce relationships which express the arbitrary functions $F(y)$, $G(y)$ etc in terms of $\phi_i(y, \lambda_i)$. It follows that under the stated assumptions concerning existence and uniqueness, the set of eigenfunctions under discussion are complete.

It is shown that the eigenfunctions generated by the even ordered systems examined here satisfy the following set of equation: $\langle \omega_{\alpha\beta} \phi_\beta \rangle = \delta_{\alpha\beta} \langle \omega_{\alpha\beta} \phi_\alpha \rangle$ where $\delta_{\alpha\beta}$ is Kronecker delta, $\omega_{\alpha\beta}$ is the weight functions which depend on λ_α and λ_β while brackets indicate integration over the y -span. This is claimed to be a general formulation of the orthogonality. Indeed, that formulation holds when the eigenfunctions are generated by Sturm–Liouville system. In such a case the weight function is ω_α does not depend on the on λ_β , and it consists of product of the ϕ_α times a negative function of y . The weight functions are independent of λ_β , but different from those type. The Sturm–Liouville

orthogonality for the fourth and sixth order of eigenfunctions introduced herein.

Key Words

High order Eigenfunctions and Eigenvalues, Papkovich–Fadle functions, Orthogonality, Self functions, Unique functions

1 Introduction

Before the appearance of Papkovich's (1940), Fadle's (1940), and Smith's (1952) papers on the so called biorthogonal series, the attention of mathematicians was focused on the second order eigenfunctions, i.e. those generated by the homogeneous differential systems of that order. Other order eigenfunctions were studied but not extensively or methodically. For example, the stability of a layer of fluid heated below, as well as that of elastic column under a buckling forces, were known to be governed by homogeneous sixth and fourth order differential system. In Budak et al (1988) dealing with various fourth order equation mostly missing the odd terms and hence can be under situations as second order. In fluid mechanics governing equations of higher order also appear (Bar-Meir 2021a) as well in compressible flow (Bar-Meir 2021b), and, ship stability (Bar-Meir 2021c). Even in cases where at first glance it should not be used like (Bar-Meir and Brauner 2021; Bar-Meir 2012a; Bar-Meir 2012b). But since stability criteria are associated with the lowest eigenfunctions very little effort was made to analyze the higher ones or the properties of second order eigenfunctions, and implicit use of their completeness was made as early as the 1750's. For it is around that time the d'Alambert, Euler and Bernoulli developed the solutions for vibrating string problem in the terms of Fourier

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Series.

Seventy years later Sturm–Liouville Theorem was published. It was thus shown that the Fourier Series is not in a class by itself, because there is virtually no end to complete orthogonal sets of eigenfunctions that second order differential systems of a certain type can generate. With this Theorem as basic tool big strides were made in the fields of heat transfer, acoustics, potential theory and most importantly, quantum mechanics. Probably because one could get rather far with second order eigenfunctions, virtually no effort was made to study higher order ones. Yet it is possible, in fact probable, that with a broader mathematical foundation many more physical phenomena will be analyzable.

This survey casts the Papkovitch–Fadle Series in a light different to that in which it is usually being viewed. It is much more than a tool for calculating the deflection of a plate or certain Stokesian flow. The development of this series, as well as the related one considered by Joseph and Fosdick (1973), represent the first serious break away from the two century long concentrated attention on second order eigenfunctions. The purpose of this work is to enhance this refreshing departure. Accordingly, the properties of various third, fourth, and sixth order eigenfunctions are studied. Of these some are introduced here. Other have encountered but have not been studied in depth. Also, a fresh treatment is provided to the Papkovitch–Fadle series, which has been investigated rather extensively. All these cases are treated by one and the same method and thus a systematic approach to this topic is laid out.

Note that it is easy to identify eigenfunctions. One often encounters such. Moreover, one can simply postulate an ordinary differential system over a finite y range, which contains a parameters λ and for which there are non-trivial solutions $\phi(y; \lambda_i)$ when λ assumes the values $\lambda = \lambda_i, i = 1, 2, 3 \dots$. The difficulty is to state something definite about their properties, and in particular about their orthogonality and completeness as a set; it is in this sense that the approach proposed is useful. It is based on the premise that in studying eigenfunctions one should not restrict one's investigation to the ordinary differential system generating them. Indeed that broader view can be more rewarding, was shown by Gregory (1980), by constructing the biharmonic solution for the two dimensional strip $-1 < y < 1$ and $-\infty < x < \infty$ he proved the completeness of the Papkovitch–Fadle series. But while, in this case consideration of the broader problem is natural, for it is interest in the biharmonic strip problem that motivated the extensive studies of the Papkovitch–Fadle series, sometimes there is no natural boundary–value problem to provide a broader problems have to be invented.

This is repeatedly done in his work as follows. Let there be a strip $-1 < y < 1$ and $0 < x < \infty$ over which the function $\psi(x, y)$ is defined. The partial differential equation governing ψ and the conditions imposed at the long edges are such that, when the solution $\psi(x, y)$ varies in the x direction like $\exp(-\lambda x)$, then its y dependence is governed by the ordinary homogeneous dif-

ferential system which is to be studied. At the short edge, $x = 0$ and $-1 < y < 1$, as many conditions as necessary are imposed in terms of data functions $F(y), G(y)$, etc. Therefore, in as much as the solution for $\psi(x, y)$ is expressible as the sum of products of the type $\phi(y; \lambda_i x)$, (and this is not always the case) then the coefficients in these expansions are in the form of integrals involving F, G etc ... Consequently, by formally setting $x = 0$ and thus recovering the edge conditions from the solution for $\psi(x, y)$, one gets relationships expressing F, G etc as eigenfunctions–expansions. The coefficients in the latter have the above said dependence on F, G etc. This (these) relationship(s) are, of course, far more informative than the ordinary homogeneous differential system postulated for encountered.

Two points concerning this approach must be noted. The first is the contravariability of the setting $x = 0$ in the expressions representing the solution in $0 < x < \infty, 0 < y < 1$. To prove that one can indeed thus recover the prescribed condition(s) one must first ascertain that the solution for ψ exists and that it is unique; this not done here. The second point is that although the strip problems provide broader views, it is the ordinary homogeneous differential system that mold the eigenfunctions and determine their properties. This is shown by broadening the ordinary system, which generates the Papkovitch–Fadle series, to three different strip–problems. Of these two are classical biharmonic and the third is invented. But all the broader problems considered yield the very same relationships between F, G and the eigenfunctions $\phi(y; \lambda_i)$.

Churchill (1958) and authors of the other texts also examine strip problems and thus gather information about the reduced homogeneous ordinary systems and the eigenfunctions that these generates. However, while these cite a standard treatment which is applicable to all second order Sturm–Liouville systems, here each ordinary differential system has to be separately analyzed. Hopefully, despite the tedious case–by–case plodding, the generality of the approach proposed will be noted. Indeed, as explained, all cases are analyzed in a similar manner. Furthermore, this unified approach leads to a very general set of relationships of $\langle \omega_\alpha \phi_\beta \rangle = \delta_{\alpha\beta} \langle \omega_\alpha \phi_\alpha \rangle$ expressing the orthogonality.

2 Standard Analysis

The mathematical procedure described at the end of the last section is repeated in the course of the work. Therefore, it will be carried out in detail only in one case and traced rather briefly in all others. The case chosen as a standard example is the following fourth

$$\left(\frac{d^2}{dy^2} + \lambda^2 \right) \frac{d^2 \phi}{dy^2} = 0 \quad \begin{cases} -1 < y < 1 \\ \phi = \phi' = 0 \\ y = 0, 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

For a long time it was known to govern the buckling instability of a built-in column. A broad boundary value problem shedding light on this system was rather recently encountered by Tuck and Bentwich (1983) in their study of a certain channel flow. For in that work they solve for the stream function which is governed by:

$$\frac{\partial^4 \psi}{\partial y^4} - \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial y^2 \partial x} = 0 \quad -1 < y < 1 \quad 0 < x < \infty \quad (2a)$$

$$\psi = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} = 0 \quad y = -1, 1 \quad 0 < x < \infty \quad (2b)$$

$$\psi(0, y) = F(y) \quad -1 < y < 1 \quad (2c)$$

Hence when ψ varies with x like $\exp(-\lambda x)$ the problem defined by relationships section 2 reduces to system eq. (1).

The x -wise Laplace Transform of the $\psi(x, y)$, $\overline{\psi(s, y)}$ is evidently governed by

$$\left(\frac{d^2}{dy^2} - s \right) dy^2 = -F''(y) \quad (3)$$

and satisfies conditions eq. (2b) at the two ends. The solution for the transformation $\overline{\psi}$ can be expressed in terms of Green's function as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\psi(s, y)} &= \frac{1}{\sinh(2\sqrt{s})} \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \\ &\int_{-1}^y \sinh(\sqrt{s}(\eta + 1)) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(\eta - 1)) F(\eta) d\eta + \\ &\frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \int_y^1 \sinh(\sqrt{s}(\eta + 1)) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(\eta - 1)) F(\eta) d\eta \\ &- \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \int_{-1}^1 \cosh(\sqrt{s}\eta) F(\eta) [\cosh(\sqrt{s}) - \cosh(\sqrt{s}y)] d\eta \\ &+ \cosh(\sqrt{s}) \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\sinh(\sqrt{s}\eta)}{\sinh(\sqrt{s} - \cosh(\sqrt{s}y))} F(\eta) d\eta \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

That transformation possesses a unique inverse which is expressible as the sum of residues of the product $\exp(zx)\overline{\psi(z, y)}$ in the left half of the complex z plane. This product appears to have simple poles at $z = m^2\pi^2/4$ where m is an integer so that $\sinh(2\sqrt{z})$ vanishes there. It also has poles at $z = -\alpha_j^2$ where $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, where α_j is the j^{th} roots of the following transcendental equation

$$\tan(\alpha) - \alpha = 0 \quad (5)$$

so that for $\sqrt{s} = i\alpha_j$ $[\sinh(\sqrt{s}) - (\sqrt{s}/2) \cosh(\sqrt{s})]$ vanishes. However, when m is odd the first three integrals on the r.h.s. of eq. (4) cancel out while $\cosh(\sqrt{s})$, which multiples forth, vanishes. Therefore, it is only when m is even that the product under examination has poles due to the vanishing of $\sinh(2\sqrt{s})$. In such cases the contributions of the first two terms are canceled by that of the last. The third term reduces to the products $\phi_n \exp(-n^2\pi^2 x)$ where the eigenfunctions ϕ_n are even in y . The products $\phi_j \exp(-\alpha_j^2 x)$, where ϕ_j are odd in y , emerges due to the residues associated with forth integral in the relationship eq. (4) at $z = -\alpha_j^2$.

The resulting solution for the strip problem (2)–(2b) is consequently

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x, y) &= - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sinh(\alpha_j)} \int_{-1}^1 F(\eta) \sin(\alpha_j \eta) \psi(y; \alpha_j) e^{-\alpha_j^2 x} d\eta \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \int_{-1}^1 F(\eta) \cos(n\pi) e^{n^2\pi^2 x} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

where the odd and even eigenfunctions are defined as follows

$$\phi_j = \phi(y, \alpha_j) \equiv y \sinh(\alpha_j) - \sin(\alpha_j y) \quad (7)$$

$$\phi_n = \phi(y, n\pi) \equiv \cos(n\pi y) - (-1)^n \quad (8)$$

This is a derivation of the solution as a sum of products $\phi_j \exp(-\lambda_j^2 x)$ and it is therefore akin to that of Gregory (1980). However, it is dissimilar to Benthem's solution (1963) which is assumed to be in the form of such sum of products.

To show that eigenfunctions of the system of eq. (1) are orthogonal consider a sequence of solutions for ψ each consisting of single products $\phi_j(y, \alpha_j) \exp(-\alpha_j^2 x)$ or $\phi_n(y, 2n\pi) \exp(-n^2\pi^2 x)$. Every such solution is expressible by the summation eq. (6) in which the coefficient of the single non vanishing product is unity. Assuming uniqueness, the coefficients of all the other products in that expansion vanish. It follows that the following relationships hold

$$\delta_{ji} = \int_{-1}^1 \sin(\alpha_j \xi) \phi_i d\xi \quad (9)$$

$$\delta_{nm} = \int_{-1}^1 \cos(2n\pi \xi) \phi_m d\xi \quad (10)$$

where the terms on the left are Kronecker deltas. Nothing that the integral of products of odd/even weight function times even/odd eigenfunctions vanish one gets

$$\langle \omega_\alpha \pi_\beta \rangle = \delta_{\alpha\beta} \langle \omega_\alpha \phi_\alpha \rangle \quad (11)$$

Here ω_α is the weight function $\sin(\alpha_j \xi)$ or $\cos(n\pi \xi)$ while the brackets signifies integration over the span under discussion. As pointed out this form of orthogonality also holds for host of other sets eigenfunctions.

It is conjectured that the set of eigenfunctions generated by the differential system eq. (1) is also complete. To be precise, given a function $F(y)$ which vanishes at the end $y(\pm 1)$, has finite derivatives and it continuous, except possibly at the finite number points in the range of $-1 < y < 1$, then it can be expressed within the range $-1 < y < 1$ as follows

$$F(y) = \sum_k \frac{\langle \omega_k \rangle}{\langle \omega_k \phi_k \rangle} \phi_k(y, \lambda_k) \quad (12)$$

The last relationship is obtained by formally setting in the solution eq. (6) $x = 0$. For $F(y)$ satisfying the above said requirements a Laplace Transform in the from eq. (4) can be obtained. Furthermore it can verified that this transform, satisfies

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} s \overline{\phi(s, y)} = F(y) \quad (13)$$

It therefore follows from the well known theorem, that the inverse $\psi(x, y)$ converges to $F(y)$ as x approaches zero. As explained in the introduction, this chain of arguments cannot be invoked without ascertaining that the solution for the strip problem exists and it unique. Since the arguments presented are not water-tight it is instructive to consider an example. Let function F be defined as follows

$$F = \begin{cases} 1, & -1/2 < y < 1/2 \\ 0, & 1/2 < |y| < 1 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

So that it is sectionally continuous. Calculating the coefficients in expansion eq. (12) using the orthogonal relationship eq. (11), with the appropriate weight functions and the value $\langle \omega_n \phi_n \rangle$ as implicitly given by equation eq. (10), one gets

$$F = \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2m+1} (-1)^m (\cos[(2m+1)\pi y] + 1) \quad (15)$$

Now it is well known that the constant terms add up to one half while the y dependent terms add up to a rectangular shaped wave pattern of amplitude, eq. (14) and eq. (15) are identical.

3 Sixth and Third Order System

Consider the ordinary homogeneous differential system

$$\frac{d^4}{dy^4} \left(\frac{d^2}{dy^2} + \lambda^2 \right) \phi = 0 \quad (16)$$

with boundary conditions of

$$\phi = \phi' = \phi'' = 0 \quad @y = \pm 1 \quad (17)$$

It obviously has a y -antisymmetrical set eigenfunctions which are given by

$$\phi_n = \sin(p_n y) + \left(\frac{y^3 p_n^2}{6} - y \left(\frac{p_n^2}{6} + 1 \right) \right) \sin(p_n) \quad (18)$$

where p_n is the n th root of

$$(p) \cos(p) + \left(\frac{p^2}{3} - 1 \right) \sin(p) = 0 \quad (19)$$

It also generates symmetric eigenfunctions which are given by

$$\phi_m = \cos(q_m y) + \left(-\frac{q_m^2}{2} + 1 + \frac{q_m^2 y^2}{2} \right) \cos(q_m) \quad (20)$$

where q_m is the m th root of

$$(q) \cos(q) - \sin(q) = 0 \quad (21)$$

The point made in this article is that this is almost as far as one can reach in the investigation of the differential system eq. (16)-(17) as it stands. i.e. not in the context of a broad boundary value problem. Admittedly, with a bit of ingenuity and luck one can discover that the eigenfunctions are orthogonal in the following

sense

$$\int_{-1}^1 \sin(p_j y) \phi_i(y; p_1) dy = \frac{p_j^2 \sin^2(p_j)}{9} \delta_{ij} \quad (22)$$

$$\int_{-1}^1 \cos(q_j y) \phi_i(y; q_i) dy = \sin^2(q_j) \delta_{ij}$$

In this case too, the integrals of the even/odd weight function times an odd/even eigenfunctions vanish. Consequently if the eigenfunctions are suitably normalized also be compactly expressed by the eq. (11). However, such guesswork leaves unclear as to the origin of the weight function $\sin(p_j y)$ and $\cos(q_j y)$. Furthermore, one is left in the dark as to whether the set consisting of $\phi(y, p_n)$ together with $\phi(y, q_m)$ is eligible for completeness. Clarification is obtained by considering the solution for $\psi(x, y)$ that satisfies

$$\left(\frac{\partial^6}{\partial y^6} - \frac{\partial^5}{\partial y^4 \partial x} \right) \psi = 0 \quad (23)$$

throughout the strip $-1 < y < 1$ and $0 < x < \infty$, has vanishing second, first and zeroth derivatives at $y = \pm 1$. In this case the solution for $\psi(x, y)$ does not represent a known physical situation that the authors knows of. This boundary value problems was invented in order to study the properties of the eigenfunctions generated by the ordinary differential system eq. (17).

Following the procedure detailed in the last section one can show that the Laplace Transform of ψ is given by

$$\overline{\psi(s, y)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s} \sinh(2\sqrt{s})}$$

$$\left[\int_1^y \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1-y)) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1+\eta)) F(\eta) d\eta + \int_1^y \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1-\eta)) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1+y)) F(\eta) d\eta \right]$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2 [\sqrt{s} \cosh(\sqrt{s}) - (1+s/3) \sinh(\sqrt{s})]}$$

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{\sinh(\sqrt{s}\eta) F(\eta) d\eta}{\sinh(\sqrt{s})}$$

$$\left[\sinh(\sqrt{s}y) + \left(\frac{s}{6} - 1 \right) y - \left(\frac{sy^3}{6} \right) \sinh(\sqrt{s}) \right] +$$

$$\frac{1}{2 [\sqrt{s} \sinh(\sqrt{s}) - (s) \cosh(\sqrt{s})]} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\cosh(\sqrt{s}\eta) F(\eta) d\eta}{\cosh(\sqrt{s})}$$

$$\left[\cosh(\sqrt{s}y) + \left(\left(\frac{s}{2} - 1 \right) - \frac{sy^2}{2} \right) \cosh(\sqrt{s}) \right] \quad (24)$$

Again $\exp(zx) \overline{\psi(z, y)}$ has no residues at $\sqrt{s} = in\pi$ where either $\sinh(\sqrt{s})$ or $\cosh(\sqrt{s})$ and hence also $\sinh(2\sqrt{s})$ vanish. On the other hand, there are residues at $\sqrt{s} = ip_n$ and $\sqrt{s} = iq_m$ where the multipliers of the integrals over $-1 < \eta < 1$ are singular. By summing these one gets the following standard form of solution

$$\psi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n \langle \omega_n F \rangle \phi_n \exp(-p_n^2 x) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} C_m \langle \omega_m F \rangle \phi_m \exp(-q_m^2 x) \quad (25)$$

where C_n and C_m depend on p_n and q_m , respectively. Thus with these values of \sqrt{s} the integrals over $-1 < \eta < 1$ of relationship eq. (22) reduces to those of relationships eq. (24) which contain the weight functions $\sin(p_n \eta)$ and $\cos(q_m \eta)$. These are therefore derived rather than guessed. To show that the latter set of relationships hold, and hence the orthogonality of the form eq. (11) is applicable, consider as in the last section, a sequence of solutions of ψ in the form of single product. From this process one also gathers that the integrated products $\langle \omega_i \phi_i \rangle$ are equal to the coefficients C_i that were obtained in the course of the residues calculation. Furthermore, the arguments supporting the conjecture concerning completeness holds in the is case too.

This section is concluded with a brief discussion of the following third order differential system.

$$\frac{d}{dy} \left(\frac{d^2}{dy^2} + \lambda^2 \right) \phi = 0 \quad \phi(-1) = \phi'(-1) = \phi(1) = 0 \quad (26)$$

Little is known about the homogeneous solutions of this or other systems of that order and the results derived are not claimed to particularly significant or useful. However, that this study does demonstrate it that a lot more is gathered by examining system eq. (26) in the context of a boundary value problem in a strip than as it stands. Indeed, by following the course proposed one finds that the system under discussion generates homogeneous solution solutions of dissimilar nature to those generated by system eq. (1) and eq. (16). Nevertheless their behavior is tractable.

A set of eigenfunctions satisfying the equation and conditions of the differential system eq. (26) is clearly given by

$$\phi_n = \cos(\sqrt{s}(1+y)) - 1 \quad (27)$$

where n runs over all integers. However, there appears to be none other and yet these do not a complete set. Indeed, the set generated by the system eq. (1) is eligible for a completeness because apart from the eigenfunctions ϕ_n which are symmetric in y . It

also contains the antisymmetric ones ϕ_j . Consequently system eq. (26), and possibly all third order systems or a large class of these, appear to generate an incomplete set of eigenfunctions (or semi-complete because it can represent an arbitrary sectionally continuous function only if it is symmetric in y). But while this much is gathered by studying system eq. (26) as it stands one can derive the functions that completes the set by considering the strip problem. Let ψ be governed by

$$\left(\frac{\partial^3}{\partial y^3} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y \partial x} \right) \psi = 0 \quad (28)$$

and let it satisfy the following short edge condition

$$\psi(0, y) = F(y) \quad (29)$$

together with the appropriate ones along the long edges. Its Laplace Transform is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\psi(s, y)} &= \frac{\sqrt{s}}{1 - \cosh(2\sqrt{s})s} \int_{-1}^1 F(\eta) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 - \eta)) \\ &\quad (1 - \cosh(1 + \sqrt{s}y)) d\eta - \frac{\sqrt{s}}{\sinh(2\sqrt{s})} \int_{-1}^y F(\eta) \left[\right. \\ &\quad \left. (\sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 - \eta) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 + y))) - \right. \\ &\quad \left. (\sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 - y)) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 - y)) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 + \eta))) \right] d\eta \\ &\quad - \left\{ \int_y^1 F(\eta) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 - \eta)) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 + y)) d\eta \right\} - \\ &\quad \int_y^1 F(\eta) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 + \eta) \sinh(\sqrt{s}(1 - y)) d\eta \quad (30) \end{aligned}$$

which appears to have poles at $2\sqrt{s} = in\pi$, because when n is an integer and $\sinh(\sqrt{s})$ vanishes. But for these values of \sqrt{s} the expression in the curly bracket vanishes too. Therefore, the only poles which contribute to the sum of residues that constitutes $\psi(x, y)$ are those located at $\sqrt{s} = 2im\pi$ where the expression $(1 - \cosh(2\sqrt{s}))$ vanishes. But these poles are of the second

order. Therefore the solution of the ψ has the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \exp \left\{ (-n^2 \pi^2 x) \int_{-1}^1 F(\eta) \left(\sin(n\pi(1 - \eta)) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. (2n\pi x)(1 - \cos(n\pi(1 + y))) + \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. (y + 1) \sin(n\pi(1 + y)) \right) d\eta \right\} \\ &\quad - \int_{-1}^1 F(\eta)(1 - \eta) \cos(n\pi\eta)(1 - \cos(n\pi(1 + y))) d\eta \quad (31) \end{aligned}$$

which is more complicated than those derived above.

Setting $(x = 0)$ one gets a relationship expressing F as an expansion in ϕ_n and $y \sin(2n\pi y)$. It follows that the set consisting of the functions of both types is eligible for completeness. But the functions $y \sin(2n\pi y)$ are not eigenfunctions in the conventional sense. For they satisfy the conditions but not the governing equation of system eq. (26). Moreover, they are orthogonal but not in the sense defined by eq. (11). In fact, the exact relationships defining this property in the case at hand is obtained by considering, as before, a sequence of solutions for ψ satisfying the governing equation and the long edge conditions. They are in the forms of products of the following types

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &= \phi_n \exp(-4n^2 \pi^2 x), \\ &\quad ((4n\pi x)\phi_n + y \sin(2n\pi y)) \exp(-4n^2 \pi^2 x) \quad (32) \end{aligned}$$

The resulting relationships expressing the orthogonality are rather complicated so that in the interest of brevity, they will not be spelled out.

4 The Papkovich Fadde Series

These are generated by the following ordinary homogeneous differential system

$$\left(\frac{d^2}{dy^2} + \lambda^2 \right)^2 \phi = 0 \quad \phi = \phi' = 0 \quad y = -1, 1 \quad (33)$$

They are studied here by the considering the three semi-infinite strip problems. In one the dependent variable ψ is governed by

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right)^2 \psi = 0 \quad (34)$$

throughout the domain, has vanishing zeroth and first derivatives along the long edges and satisfies the following short edge conditions.

$$\psi = F(y) \quad \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = -G(y) \quad @x = 0 \quad (35)$$

This does not represent a known physical phenomenon, but the other two problems are the classical biharmonic and their solutions could, for example, represent the deflection of a plate. When the short edge conditions are

$$\psi = H(y) \quad \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = J(y) \quad @x = 0 \quad (36)$$

The deflection and the moment are prescribed. When the slope and the shear force are given, the following hold

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = K(y) \quad \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial x^3} = L(y) \quad @x = 0 \quad (37)$$

Laplace Transform the first strip problem one gets

$$\left(\frac{d^2}{dy^2} - s\right)^2 \overline{\psi(s,y)} = [-2F'' + sF - G] \\ \overline{\psi} = \frac{\partial \overline{\psi}}{\partial y} = 0 \quad y = 0, 1 \quad (38)$$

Remarkably similar inhomogeneous ordinary differential system govern the Fourier Sine and Fourier cosine Transform of the two biharmonic problems. These read

$$\left(\frac{d^2}{dy^2} - \alpha^2\right)^2 \overline{\psi_s(\alpha,y)} = \alpha [-2H'' + \alpha^2 H - J] \\ \frac{\partial \overline{\psi_s}}{\partial y} = \overline{\psi_s} = 0 \quad y = 0, 1 \quad (39)$$

$$\left(\frac{d^2}{dy^2} - \alpha^2\right)^2 \overline{\psi_c(\alpha,y)} = \alpha [2K'' - \alpha^2 K + L] \\ \frac{\partial \overline{\psi_c}}{\partial y} = \overline{\psi_c} = 0 \quad y = 0, 1 \quad (40)$$

The solution is, rather complicated so for sake of clarity and brevity, not spell out. It can be easily shown that despite the presence of the factor $1/(\alpha^2 \sinh \alpha)$ these transforms are not singular at $\alpha = in\pi$ where n is an integer. Hence the inverse of these is obtainable by summing the residues of $\exp(zx)\overline{\psi(z,y)}2\exp(i\alpha x)\overline{\psi_s(\alpha,y)}2\exp(i\alpha x)\overline{\psi_c(\alpha,y)}$ at the poles where $(\alpha - \sinh \alpha)$ and $(\alpha + \sinh \alpha)$ vanish in the left half complex z plane and the top half of the complex α plane. These poles are at $z = -p_n^2$ and $z = -q_m^2$ or else at $\alpha = ip_n$ and $\alpha = iq_m$ where p_n and q_m are the roots of

$$p_n - \sin(p_n) \cos(p_n) = 0 \quad (41)$$

$$q_m + \sin(q_m) \cos(q_m) = 0 \quad (42)$$

Consequently the three solutions sought are

$$\psi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{\sin^4 p_n}\right) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} < (2F'' + p_n^2 F + G)\phi_n > \\ < (2H'' + p_n^2 F + J)\phi_n > \\ - < (2K'' + p_n^2 K + L)\phi_n/p_n > \end{array} \right\} \\ \times \phi_n(y, p_n) \exp \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -p_n^2 x \\ -p_n x \\ -p_n x \end{array} \right\} - \\ \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{\cos^4 q_m}\right) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} < (2F'' + q_m^2 F + G)\phi_m > \\ < (2H'' + q_m^2 F + J)\phi_m > \\ - < (2K'' + q_m^2 K + L)\phi_m/p_m > \end{array} \right\} \\ \times \phi_m(y, q_m) \exp \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -q_m^2 x \\ -q_m x \\ -p_m x \end{array} \right\} \quad (43)$$

Expectedly, all the three solutions are expressed in terms of eigenfunctions which are odd and even in y and defined, respectively, as follows

$$\phi(y, p_n) = \cos(p_n) \sin(p_n y) - y \sin(p_n) \cos(p_n y) \\ \phi(y, q_m) = \sin(q_m) \cos(q_m y) - y \sin(q_m) \cos(p_n y) \quad (44)$$

Proceeding as before one considers a sequence of solutions for ψ that satisfy equation eq. (34) or biharmonic equation. These are, respectively, $\phi_i \exp(-r_i^2)$ or $\phi_i(-r_1 x)$ where r_1 stands for either p_n or q_m . Thus they also satisfy the long edge conditions and reduce to those imposed along the short edge, eq. (23) eq. (37), and eq. (39) for $x = 0$. Driving the data function F, G, J, H, K and L from the latter relationship one finds that the eigenfunctions defined by equation eq. (40) satisfy the general form of

the orthogonal relationships

$$\langle \omega_{ij} \phi_i \rangle = \delta_{ij} \langle \omega_{ij} \phi_i \rangle \quad (45)$$

where in this case the weight function ω_{ij} depends on two eigenfunctions r_1 and r_i these are given by

$$\omega_{ij} = 2 \left(\frac{d^2 \phi_1}{dy^2} + (r_i^2 + r_j^2) \right) \phi_j \quad (46)$$

The non-vanishing integrated products are

$$\langle \omega_{ij} \phi \rangle = -2 \sin^4(p_i) - 2 \cos^4(q_j) \quad (47)$$

When $\phi(y, r_i)$, and therefore also ω_{ij} , are odd and even in y , respectively.

5 Summary

It has been shown that by treating ordinary homogeneous differential systems in the broader context of the a boundary value problem, useful information about their eigenfunctions can be obtained. Unfortunately the proposed process hinges on the algebraically involved construction of solutions to systems eq. (3) (38) (39) and (40) and their like. There is an available method by which one can construct a Green's function type of solution to these, but it is applicable only when the inhomogeneous differential system is of order two. Thus, the task of studying forth, sixth and higher order eigenfunctions becomes progressively more difficult. Consequently, although the results reported suggest that the course chosen is promising; it has yet to be perfected and generalized in order to become useful.

While one is not in a position to make general statements concerning the properties of the eigenfunctions of order higher than two, the recurrence of form eq. (11) cannot be ignored. In fact, it clearly implies that there is a class of sets of eigenfunctions which satisfy this type of orthogonality. More that class includes all those generated by the Sturm–Liouville systems where in these cases the weight function are

$$\omega_i = f(y) \phi(y, \lambda_i) \quad (48)$$

and $f(y)$ is a non negative function which appears in the governing equation. in the search for the exact definition of that class the treatment of system eq. (26) is important. Firstly, because it generates a set of eigenfunctions which are orthogonal in a different sense (assuming the functions $y \sin(2n\pi y)$ are included in the set). Secondly, because it appears to suggest that all third

and other odd order homogeneous system are not including in the class to which the orthogonality of the form eq. (11) is applicable.

In delineating that, somewhat elusive, class it is important to identify its known members. The Papkovich–Fadle set of eigenfunctions is one. It is therefore misleading to name these biorthogonal, to express their orthogonality by two sets relationships or by any formulation other than eq. (11). These are orthogonal in the same sense that, say, members of Fourier Series are and there is nothing dual or bi about their orthogonality. Indeed the two sets of equations (2.9) and (2.10) proposed by Spencer (1983) can be easily verified using the single set eq. (11).¹ So can the rather complicate formulation of the so called biorthogonality suggested by Joseph (1977) where use is made of two–by–two matrix. Of course there is something dual about the Papkovich–Fadle eigenfunctions. For it is well known that in order to determine that coefficients in an expansion of these, two data functions are needed, while only one is required to determine the coefficient in, say, a Fourier series. But this has nothing to do with the orthogonality. The later property is just an analytical tool by means of which the data function (or functions) is (are) related to the coefficients. Thus, when that analytical method is inapplicable one can evaluate the coefficient by computer calculation and in Spencer (1983) it is explained how that is done. But irrespective of the manner of the calculations a single expansion of the latter type is determinable by, and therefore also represents, two distributions defined over a range $-1 < y < 1$. Therefore the correct description of that series is not ‘biorthogonal’ but ‘bi–representative’ or ‘bideterminate’.

This feature becomes immediately recognizable once the differential system eq. (33) is broadened to a boundary value problem in a strip as has been advocated throughout this work. By the way, this feature is far more noticeable when ψ satisfies eq. (34) rather than the biharmonic governing equation.

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Concluding Remarks

This article was supposed to be published about 1987 while the second author was a master student in Tel Aviv University. At the time, the second author took a class from Bentwich dealing

¹Spencer paper is available online.

with eigenfunctions (heat transfer). This problem was given as an extra half-baked question (on the paper probably completed in Bentwich's mind.). Bentwich passed away prematurely at end of that semester. Since then even the other inspiring individual of this work (see Acknowledgment) Professor Ernest Oliver (Ernie) Tuck also had passed away. The material moved from one place to another with the second author and finally is brought to life. All the mistakes and typos are responsibility of the second author. The ideas should be attribute to **Professor** Micheal Bentwich. The second author is only a poor conduit to pass these ideas from the past. During the past time, some of the notes have been lost and had to be reconstructed and thus introduced further more errors. If you find an error please pass it to the second author so they could be corrected. There are other papers by Bentwich (as the main author) which are in a process bringing them to print. These areas are more of mathematics rather than the natural area of the second author and hence they would not be not as good as they should be if Bentwich was able to finish them. Because of that, this paper should be viewed more as proof of concept for eigenfunctions of higher order and their orthogonality and the self functions of odd order equations. That is, functions that come out from the partial equations and not from the systems they created.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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